

Energy poverty alleviation in social housing: Prototyping policies with practitioners

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1. Introduction

The European energy crisis of 2022 stresses the importance of protecting the most vulnerable households. Price peaks disproportionately affect households with low incomes, limited savings, and inefficient homes, and increased energy poverty: the inability to secure sufficient domestic energy services that allow for participation in society (Bouzarovski & Petrova, 2015).

Since European social housing countries have become increasingly residualised, a significant share of households in or at risk of energy poverty are being accommodated by social housing providers (Poggio & Whitehead, 2017; Walker, 2008). However, while most practitioners acknowledge that social housing providers (SHPs) have a responsibility in energy poverty alleviation, targeted intervention approaches have hardly been explored (Desvallées, 2022). The body of scholarship on energy poverty measurement has grown rapidly, but its use in practice has hardly been addressed (Bouzarovski et al., 2021). Sherriff et al. (2019) note that a possible explanation might be that insights from research are inadequately communicated to policymakers and practitioners. Charlier and Legendre (2021) add that the sense of urgency has substantially differed across countries.

This paper aims to combat these gaps, by proactively engaging with practitioners across Europe to find out which targeted intervention approaches are considered most effective, what their benefits and potential (regulatory) obstacles are, and whether these perspectives differ in different policy contexts. We indirectly examine the responsibilities SHPs are willing to accept within a 'just transition', and explore whether, and if so how, their apparent techno-economic approach to retrofit provision could be altered (De Feijter et al., 2019).

2. Policy prototyping

Generally, research strategies are based on either a deductive or an inductive approach to science (Bryman, 2016). While the former offers 'reliability' and the latter indicates 'probability', it could be argued that both miss the notion of 'possibility' (Barry & Hansen, 2008, p. 457). Peirce (1965) therefore developed his abductive approach to develop 'tentative explanatory hypotheses' or 'proto-theories' and initiate novel research trajectories. In policymaking, deductive approaches (testing policy interventions through randomised controlled trials) or inductive approaches (exploring why these did or did not work) could be complemented with abductive approaches (Bason, 2014). Exploring new policy interventions ('musement' in Peirce's words) and making provisional guesses on their effects are key (Kimbell, 2015).

Abductive approaches are often based on participatory research design. First, a carefully selected mix of participants is asked to become part of the ‘innovation journey’, de facto acting as ‘co-researchers’ and ‘codesigners’. As abductive policy experimentation requires a holistic perspective, it is preferable to select a diverse array of participants. Then, researcher and participants collectively delve into the subject matter, starting with a definition of the desirable outcome and gradually moving towards a hypothesis of an underlying structure comprising concrete rules, arrangements, and operations.

3. Research design

At the time of submitting this conference paper, the research process is ongoing. Nevertheless, the following section presents an overview of the research design.

3.1 Focus groups

This qualitative research design incorporates six focus group sessions, referred to as ‘workshops’, as the primary data collection method. The focus groups take approximately three hours each, and their semi-structured design is set out below. They are planned in the fourth quarter of 2022.

Introduction and benchmark

In order for all participants to start the session with approximately the same understanding of the problem, we define energy poverty and describe its prevalence in social housing estates. Subsequently, we ask what data the SHP already collects and/or uses about experienced energy poverty in its stock, and what obstacles there are in collecting or using this data. We also ask participants to elaborate on current efforts of the SHP to mitigate the negative impact of the current energy crisis.

Brainstorm and prioritisation

To facilitate creative thinking, we divide the participants into three or four groups. Participants then engage in an open and candid discussion on which additional approaches their SHP could adopt. The approaches are recorded on sticky notes and displayed on a wall, and participants are asked to rank them according to their perceived potential. While part of the following semi-structured discussion is set beforehand to allow for comparison between SHPs and countries, there is room for discussion on other highly-regarded innovative approaches as well.

Semi-structured discussion

Preliminary interviews taught us several crucial approaches that have been adopted by SHPs in recent years, and we start off by discussing these approaches in detail:

- Prioritised retrofit: considering social factors (characteristics of households or neighbourhoods) besides technical or financial data in prioritising renovations.
- Strategic rent setting: considering the risk of energy poverty when setting rents, for instance based on a combination of energy efficiency and household income. Other ways of financial compensation (subsidising energy, direct allowances) can also be discussed in this round.
- Targeted allocation of dwellings: considering household income and other factors that increase risk of energy poverty (age, ability, composition) when allocating dwellings at the start of a tenancy.

However, we reserve sufficient time for the input from the previous session. After the discussion, the participants are asked to rank the various approaches again in terms of potential.

After these six focus groups are finished, the recordings are thoroughly analysed to provide insight in all possible policies and related deliberations, and to shed light on what incidental or structural obstacles must be further studied by researchers and/or addressed by policymakers before effectively targeted interventions are feasible.

3.2 Participant selection

The empirical research consists of six focus groups or ‘workshops’ in three different countries: France, the UK, and the Netherlands (Table 1). Conducting the research in different countries provides the opportunity to compare between regulatory contexts, and therefore to suggest which legislation facilitates targeted intervention in one country and obstructs it in another. We selected these three countries because of their traditionally substantial social housing sectors, and these six major SHPs because they might be able to exercise thought leadership due to their size and professionalism.

Table 1. Participating housing associations

Country	Region	Social housing provider	Rented dwellings
France	Countrywide	Polylogis	145,000
	Paris Metropolitan Area	Paris Habitat	125,000
United Kingdom	England	Clarion	125,000
	Greater London	Peabody	104,000
The Netherlands	Amsterdam Metropolitan Area	Ymere	75,000
	Rotterdam	Havensteder	45,000

However, their size also implies a compartmentalised organisation, which makes it even more important to select a diverse group of participants with a variety of backgrounds and perspectives. The six to eight professionals we select per workshop work in different departments and have supposedly different interests. Simply put, financial practitioners want breakeven results, legal experts want compliance with the law, and social workers want sufficient resources to protect vulnerable tenants.

Further analysis and discussion of these preliminary results will continue as part of the ongoing research undertaken in the RE-DWELL project.

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